

THE EFFECT OF SERVQUAL-BASED SERVICE QUALITY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AT BUMDES PANDAK BANDUNG

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ABSTRACT

Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) play a strategic role in driving rural economic growth; however, suboptimal service quality can affect customer satisfaction levels. This study aims to analyze the influence of service quality based on the SERVQUAL model on customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari, Tabanan Regency, Bali. The study employs a quantitative approach with a descriptive-associative design. Data were collected via a questionnaire administered to 90 active customers selected using purposive sampling. Data analysis was conducted using multiple linear regression. The results indicate that service quality simultaneously has a significant effect on customer satisfaction ($F = 27.465$; $p < 0.001$) with a coefficient of determination of 62.0%. Partially, the dimensions of tangibles, reliability, and empathy have a positive and significant effect, while responsiveness and assurance do not show a significant effect. The empathy dimension is the most dominant factor in increasing customer satisfaction. These findings indicate that a service approach oriented toward interpersonal relationships and understanding customer needs is a crucial factor in improving the quality of BUMDes services in community-based environments.

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1. INTRODUCTION

BUMDes is a village enterprise managed with capital contributions from segregated village assets, aimed at developing economic potential and improving the welfare of the village community. Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes) are village business entities established to manage economic activities and optimize village assets for community welfare. Their existence and governance are regulated under Law No. 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, as amended by Law No. 3 of 2024, and Government Regulation No. 11 of 2021 concerning Village-Owned Enterprises. From a strategic management perspective, the role of BUMDes is not merely viewed as a business entity but as an instrument for community empowerment capable of competing with the private sector in terms of efficiency and service quality (Mulyadi et al., 2023). Pratama & Wijaya (2024) state that the main challenges frequently faced by BUMDes are the lack of professional human resources (HR) and the absence of standardized Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs). Consequently, these conditions directly impact public perception of service quality.

BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari, located in Pandak Bandung Village, Kediri Subdistrict, Tabanan Regency, Bali, is a village economic institution managing three main business units: the Savings and Loan Unit, the Payment Services Unit (taxes, internet, electricity, and water), and the Food Security Unit. Based on registration data and pre-survey results, this BUMDes has approximately 450 active customers with an average of 30–60 transactions per day. The pre-survey identified several significant operational challenges, such as negative experiences related to service delays, long queues, and waiting times during peak hours reaching 10–20 minutes. This phenomenon indicates a gap between customer expectations and the actual performance they receive. Referring to the Service

Quality Gap Model, this gap can significantly reduce customer satisfaction levels (Tjiptono & Diana, 2020).

Dharmmesta (2022) argues that there are three key aspects to consider in service quality orientation: consumer perception, service product characteristics, and the service delivery process. The consistent application of these three aspects will lead to increased customer satisfaction, which in turn supports the long-term growth and sustainability of business entities. In line with this, Fauzi et al. (2022) explain that customer satisfaction is the primary foundation for fostering loyalty. This is particularly crucial in the context of BUMDes, given that their market base is limited to the local village community. To measure this service quality, the most commonly used method is the Service Quality (SERVQUAL) model developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1988). This model assesses service quality through five main dimensions: tangibles (physical evidence), reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy.

Previous research has consistently shown a positive influence of service quality on customer satisfaction across various BUMDes. Afika & Harmawan (2025) found a strong relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction at BUMDes Maju Sejahtera in East Java. Mabtukha & Suryaningsih (2024) state that facilities and service quality simultaneously influence customer satisfaction at BUMDes in Tulungagung. This gap is important because Bali possesses distinctive socio-cultural characteristics, including strong communal relationships through the Desa Pakraman system, a culture of mutual cooperation (gotong royong), and family-oriented interaction patterns. Such characteristics may influence how customers evaluate service quality dimensions, particularly interpersonal aspects such as empathy. Therefore, this study extends the SERVQUAL framework by integrating perspectives from relationship marketing and social capital to provide a more contextual understanding of customer satisfaction in community-based BUMDes. This integration constitutes the primary theoretical contribution of the study, as it explains service quality not only through technical service performance but also through the quality of social relationships embedded within local cultural values.

Based on this background, the research question focuses on whether overall service quality and its individual dimensions (tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy) significantly influence customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari, and which dimension most dominantly influences that satisfaction. This study aims to analyze the influence of service quality on customer satisfaction, test the partial influence of each SERVQUAL dimension, and identify the most dominant dimension in shaping customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari.

A limitation of this study is that the population scope is still limited to customers of BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari; therefore, the research results cannot be directly generalized to other BUMDes with different characteristics. This study also focuses solely on the service quality variable without incorporating other factors such as price, trust, or organizational image, and relies on respondents' perceptions via a questionnaire. Additionally, the Cronbach's Alpha values for some variables range from 0.61 to 0.62. Although this value meets the minimum threshold of >0.60 for exploratory research at the village community level (Hair et al., 2014), this is acknowledged as a limitation of the instrument, which reflects the diversity of respondents' perceptions; therefore, future research is advised to refine the questionnaire items to enhance internal consistency.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Quality of Service

According to Kotler & Keller (2018), service quality is a characteristic of a service determined by its ability to meet customer needs, whether explicitly or implicitly stated. This definition emphasizes that the success of a service is not determined by the organization's internal standards, but by the

extent to which the service meets customer expectations and perceptions. To measure this multidimensional construct, the Service Quality (SERVQUAL) model developed by Parasuraman et al. (1988) is used. This model consists of five main dimensions, namely: (1) Tangibles (physical evidence), which refers to the service provider's ability to demonstrate its existence through the physical appearance of facilities, equipment, staff, and communication materials; (2) Reliability, which is the organization's ability to deliver services as promised accurately and reliably, encompassing punctuality, consistency, and minimal errors; (3) Responsiveness, which relates to the willingness and speed of staff in assisting customers and providing clear information; (4) Assurance, encompassing employees' knowledge, courtesy, and ability to foster trust and a sense of security in customers; and (5) Empathy, which reflects personal attention, ease of communication, and a deep understanding of customers' specific needs.

2.2 Customer Satisfaction

According to Tjiptono & Diana (2020), customer satisfaction is a central concept in service marketing it is the result of comparing expectations with perceptions of product or service performance, leading to an emotional response of satisfaction or dissatisfaction. In the context of village financial institutions such as Village-Owned Enterprises (BUMDes), Tagar (2024) states that customer satisfaction is significantly influenced by the quality of service interactions, as reflected through friendliness, speed, clarity, and the ability to provide solutions, thereby enhancing customer trust and comfort. Conversely, a mismatch between expectations and service reality will lead to dissatisfaction, which ultimately results in reduced community participation. Furthermore, Amalia et al. (2020) emphasize that customer satisfaction is the key to business success, as satisfied customers are more likely to return for transactions and recommend the service to others, thereby ultimately increasing the profitability and sustainability of BUMDes.

2.3 Integration of Contextual Theory on Service Quality in a Village Setting

Morgan & Hunt (1994) argue that in community-based services, customer satisfaction is more influenced by the quality of interpersonal relationships, the level of trust, and long-term commitment between service providers and customers than by mere technical aspects of service delivery. In line with this, within the context of BUMDes services, this study not only employs the SERVQUAL model as the basis for measuring service quality but also integrates perspectives from relationship marketing and social capital. The characteristics of Balinese society, which features strong bonds within the Desa Pakraman, a culture of mutual cooperation (gotong royong), and familial communication patterns, make the empathy dimension, encompassing personal attention and understanding of needs the most relevant key variable aligned with customer expectations (Dharmmesta, 2022; Hasan et al., 2023). The integration of these theories strengthens the research analytical framework by demonstrating that increased customer satisfaction with BUMDes is not only determined by the implementation of standardized technical procedures but also by the institution's ability to build and maintain relationships grounded in local values and concern for customer needs.

2.4 Hypotheses

Based on the theoretical foundation and empirical review outlined above, this study formulates five research hypotheses. First, the Tangibles dimension is predicted to have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. This aligns with the findings of Amalia et al. (2020), who stated that physical aspects such as the comfort of facilities and the neatness of staff appearance shape initial perceptions of professionalism, which influence the overall assessment of service quality. Second, the Reliability dimension is predicted to have a positive and significant influence. Mabtukha & Suryaningsih (2024) emphasize that transaction accuracy and service consistency are

the primary foundations for building customer trust, particularly in savings and loan business units where financial accuracy is a crucial aspect.

Third, the Responsiveness dimension is predicted to have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Oswaldus & Dimas (2025) highlight that the speed in handling complaints and the responsiveness of staff are key determinants in maintaining the satisfaction levels of users of village utility services. Fourth, the Assurance dimension is predicted to have a positive and significant effect. Staff competence and courtesy play a vital role in mitigating perceptions of transaction risk, thereby enhancing a sense of security and ultimately driving customer satisfaction (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Fifth, the Empathy dimension is predicted to have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Hasan et al. (2023) state that in a collectivist cultural context such as that prevailing in Bali, interpersonal approaches and concern for customers' specific needs are highly valued, often serving as the primary determinants in shaping loyalty and satisfaction. Simultaneously, the five dimensions (tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy) are hypothesized to have a significant influence on customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari, as supported by the study by Afika & Harmawan (2025), which found a strong combined influence of all SERVQUAL dimensions

3. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Research Model

This study employs a quantitative approach using a descriptive-associative survey design. This method combines the description of variable characteristics (descriptive) with the analysis of relationships or influences between variables (associative) using data from questionnaires. This approach was chosen because the primary objective of the study is to measure and analyze the causal relationship between the service quality variable (X) and the customer satisfaction variable (Y) numerically through a questionnaire instrument (Sugiyono, 2019). This study was conducted at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari, located in Pandak Bandung Village, Kediri Subdistrict, Tabanan Regency, Bali. The selection of the location was based on the discovery of empirical phenomena related to service quality issues that have the potential to influence customer satisfaction levels, as identified in the initial pre-survey.

3.2 Sample Selection and Data Source

The sample size was determined by considering statistical adequacy for multiple linear regression analysis. Hair et al. (2014) state that the minimum recommended sample size is 10–20 times the number of independent variables being analyzed. With five independent variables, the minimum sample requirement ranges from 50–100 respondents. Additionally, Roscoe (1975) as cited in Sekaran & Bougie (2016) notes that a sample size of 30–500 respondents is considered adequate for most behavioral studies. Based on these considerations, this study utilized 90 respondents, deemed sufficient to meet the statistical requirements for producing stable and representative estimates.

The sampling technique employed purposive sampling with the following respondent criteria: (1) active customers who have made at least one transaction in the past three months; (2) aged at least 17 years or capable of conducting transactions independently. This technique was chosen because only customers directly involved with BUMDes services can provide valid assessments of service quality. This study involves two main variables: Independent Variable (X): Service quality, operationalized and analyzed through the five dimensions of SERVQUAL as independent variables, namely Tangibles (X_1), Reliability (X_2), Responsiveness (X_3), Assurance (X_4), and Empathy (X_5); and Dependent Variable (Y): Customer Satisfaction, measured through customers' perceptions of overall satisfaction.

3.3 Data Collection

This study used primary data collected through a questionnaire distributed to active customers of BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari. Data collection was conducted in person during business hours. The study population comprised all active customers of BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari residing in Pandak Bandung Village, Tabanan Regency, Bali. Based on the results of the pre-survey, it was found that the number of active customers reached 400–500 people, with an average daily transaction volume ranging from 30 to 60 transactions, particularly in the savings and loan unit and payment services.

The data collection instrument used in this study was a questionnaire designed using a Likert scale with a score range of 1 to 5. According to Sugiyono (2019), the Likert scale is used to measure the attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of an individual or group regarding a specifically defined research phenomenon. The questionnaire in this study consists of 25 statement items derived from the five dimensions of service quality (SERVQUAL) and the customer satisfaction variable. The details of these statement items include: the Tangibles dimension (X_1) with 4 items, Reliability (X_2) with 4 items, Responsiveness (X_3) with 4 items, Assurance (X_4) with 4 items, Empathy (X_5) with 4 items, and Customer Satisfaction (Y) with 5 items.

3.4 Data Analysis (Variable Measurement)

Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted using the coefficient of determination (R^2) test, the t-test (partial), and the F-test (simultaneous). The t-test (partial) was used to determine the partial effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The hypothesis is accepted if the calculated t-value > the table t-value or the significance level < 0.05. The F-test (simultaneous) was used to determine the simultaneous effect of all independent variables on the dependent variable. The hypothesis is accepted if the calculated F value is greater than the critical F value or the significance level is less than 0.05. The Coefficient of Determination (R^2) is used to measure the proportion of variation in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables collectively (Ghozali, 2018).

Data analysis in this study utilized SPSS software, which included descriptive analysis to present respondent characteristics and data distribution. Prior to hypothesis testing, prerequisite tests were conducted, including classical assumption tests (normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity) as well as a linearity test to ensure data suitability. Subsequently, multiple linear regression analysis was applied to test the influence of each dimension of service quality on customer satisfaction (Malay, 2022).

The regression equation model used is:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + e \quad (1)$$

Notes:

Y = Customer Satisfaction;

α = Constant;

β_1 – β_5 = Regression coefficients;

X_1 = Tangibles;

X_2 = Reliability;

X_3 = Responsiveness;

X_4 = Assurance;

X_5 = Empathy;

e = Error/Residual.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

The demographic data and profiles of the respondents in this study include gender, age, type of service used, and frequency of visits to BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari. The combination of these characteristic data aims to provide a comprehensive picture of the profile of customers who are the subjects of this study. The following is a summary of the respondents' characteristics presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of Study Respondents

Characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	56	62.22%
	Female	34	37.78%
Age	17-25 years	14	15.56%
	26-35 years	35	38.89%
	36-45 years	23	25.56%
	46-55 years	13	14.44%
	>55 years	5	5.55%
Services	Savings and Loans	40	44.44%
	Payment Services	39	43.33%
	Food Security	11	12.22%
Frequency	1-2 times/month	35	38.89%
	3-5 times a month	39	43.33%
	>5 times a month	16	17.78%
Total		90	100.00%

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 1, the majority of respondents were male at 62.22% (56 people), while females accounted for 37.78% (34 people). The most dominant age group is 26-35 years old at 38.89% (35 people), followed by the 36-45 age group at 25.56% (23 people). This indicates that customers of BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari are predominantly of working age and actively engaged in economic transactions. In terms of the types of services used, the majority of respondents utilized savings and loan services (44.0%) and payment services (42.9%), which are the two main business units of the BUMDes. Regarding visit frequency, 42.9% of respondents visited the BUMDes 3-5 times per month, indicating a fairly active level of engagement among customers.

Validity and Reliability Tests

Table 2. Results of Validity and Reliability Tests

Variable	Item	Calculated r	Table r (n=90)	Cronbach's alpha	Notes
Tangibles (X ₁)				0.618	Reliable
	P1	0.598	0.207		Valid
	P2	0.483	0.207		Valid
	P3	0.573	0.207		Valid
	P4	0.583	0.207		Valid
Reliability (X ₂)				0.627	Reliable
	P5	0.458	0.207		Valid
	P6	0.555	0.207		Valid

Variable	Item	Calculated r	Table r (n=90)	Cronbach's alpha	Notes
	P7	0.484	0.207		Valid
	P8	0.62	0.207		Valid
Responsiveness (X ₃)				0.611	Reliable
	P9	0.593	0.207		Valid
	P10	0.606	0.207		Valid
	P11	0.557	0.207		Valid
	P12	0.504	0.207		Valid
Assurance (X ₄)				0.611	Reliable
	P13	0.64	0.207		Valid
	P14	0.456	0.207		Valid
	P15	0.579	0.207		Valid
	P16	0.49	0.207		Valid
Empathy (X ₅)				0.615	Reliable
	P17	0.54	0.207		Valid
	P18	0.657	0.207		Valid
	P19	0.392	0.207		Valid
	P20	0.576	0.207		Valid
Customer Satisfaction (Y)				0.711	Reliable
	P21	0.545	0.207		Valid
	P22	0.657	0.207		Valid
	P23	0.617	0.207		Valid
	P24	0.585	0.207		Valid
	P25	0.526	0.207		Valid

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 2, the rtable value is 0.207 (df = 88; N = 90; α = 0.05). The validity test results show that all statement items have a calculated r value > table r value, and the reliability test shows that all variables have a Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.60. Thus, this research instrument is deemed valid and reliable for use in further analysis.

Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Tangibles (X ₁)	90	6	18	14.87	2.514
Reliability (X ₂)	90	8	19	15.29	2.623
Responsiveness (X ₃)	90	7	19	14.43	2.54
Assurance (X ₄)	90	8	19	15.5	2.469
Empathy (X ₅)	90	7	20	15.07	2.43
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	90	10	24	18.7	2,962

Source: Processed data, 2026

Descriptive statistical analysis aims to describe the research object through sample data without making generalizations (Sugiyono, 2019). Based on Table 3, all variables have relatively high mean values, indicating positive perceptions among respondents. The Assurance dimension obtained the

highest mean (15.50), reflecting high customer confidence in staff competence, followed by Reliability (15.29) and Empathy (15.07). Overall, the Customer Satisfaction (Y) variable recorded an average of 18.70. Additionally, the standard deviation values for all variables were low (2.43–2.96), indicating that respondents’ perceptions were homogeneous and consistent.

Classical Assumption Tests

Normality Test

Based on the results of the normality test conducted using the one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, a significance value of 0.200 was obtained; since this value is > 0.05, it is concluded that the residual data are normally distributed. Thus, the assumption of normality has been met in this model. The normality test aims to determine whether the residual values from the regression model are normally distributed. Data are considered normally distributed if the significance value (Sig. or p-value) is > 0.05; conversely, if the p-value is < 0.05, the data are not normally distributed (Ghozali, 2018).

Linearity Test

The researcher conducted a linearity test to determine whether the independent variables have a linear relationship with the dependent variable. The linearity test was performed to ensure that the relationship between the independent and dependent variables is linear. The test was performed using the Test for Linearity in the ANOVA analysis. The relationship between variables is considered linear if the significance value for the Linearity component is less than 0.05 and the significance value for Deviation from Linearity is greater than 0.05 (Ghozali, 2018). The test results indicate that all relationships between variables meet the linearity criteria and are therefore suitable for analysis using multiple linear regression. Based on the linearity test results conducted by the researcher, all independent variables in relation to the dependent variable yielded a significance value of 0.000, thus meeting the threshold requirement of less than 0.05. With , the assumption of linearity in this study has been met.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to determine whether there is a high correlation among the independent variables in a regression model. In a good regression model, there should be no correlation among the independent variables. Multicollinearity is detected by examining the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Tolerance values. A model is considered free of multicollinearity if the VIF value is < 10 and the Tolerance value is > 0.10 (Ghozali, 2018).

Table 4. Results of the Multicollinearity Test

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Description
Tangibles (X ₁)	0.476	2.099	Free of Multicollinearity
Reliability (X ₂)	0.575	1.738	Free of Multicollinearity
Responsiveness (X ₃)	0.443	2.259	Free of Multicollinearity
Assurance (X ₄)	0.507	1.971	Free of Multicollinearity
Empathy (X ₅)	0.541	1.848	Free of Multicollinearity

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test in Table 4, all independent variables have a Tolerance value above 0.10 and a VIF value below 10. These results indicate that there is no high correlation among the independent variables in the regression model. Thus, all research variables are free from multicollinearity issues and are suitable for use in multiple linear regression analysis.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The results of the heteroscedasticity test indicate that all independent variables have significance levels (Sig.) greater than 0.05. In the Glejser method for testing heteroscedasticity, the criterion used is that if the significance level is > 0.05, then there is no heteroscedasticity (Ghozali, 2018). Therefore, it can be concluded that the regression model does not exhibit heteroscedasticity, as all variables have significance values greater than 0.05. Thus, the regression model satisfies one of the classical assumptions of multiple linear regression.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to test the combined effect of each dimension of service quality (Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy) on customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari.

Table 5. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Variable	Coefficient (B)	Std. Error	t-value	Sig.
Constant (α)	1.378	1.5	0.919	0.361
Tangibles (X ₁)	0.228	0.115	1.989	0.05
Reliability (X ₂)	0.22	0.1	2.201	0.03
Responsiveness (X ₃)	0.086	0.118	0.727	0.469
Assurance (X ₄)	0.204	0.113	1.803	0.075
Empathy (X ₅)	0.409	0.111	3.671	0.000

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 5, the multiple linear regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = 1,378 + 0,228X_1 + 0,220X_2 + 0,086X_3 + 0,204X_4 + 0,409X_5 + e \quad (2)$$

Based on the multiple linear regression equation obtained, the constant value of 1.378 represents the baseline level of customer satisfaction when all SERVQUAL dimensions are assumed to be zero. However, because the variables were measured using a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, a zero value does not occur in practice. Therefore, the constant has limited substantive interpretation and primarily serves as a statistical component required to complete the regression equation. The regression coefficient for Tangibles (X₁) of 0.228 indicates that a one-unit increase in Tangibles will increase customer satisfaction by 0.228 units, assuming all other variables remain constant. Similarly, the coefficient for Reliability (X₂) of 0.220 means that a one-unit increase in Reliability contributes to a 0.220 increase in customer satisfaction. The Responsiveness coefficient (X₃) of 0.086 indicates a relatively smaller effect, while Assurance (X₄) contributes 0.204 units. The Empathy coefficient (X₅) of 0.409 is the largest among all predictors, indicating that Empathy is the most dominant factor influencing customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari.

Hypothesis Testing

Coefficient of Determination (R²) Test

The coefficient of determination test is used to measure the model's ability to explain the variation in the dependent variable. The higher the R² value, the greater the ability of the independent variables to explain the dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018). Based on the results of the Coefficient of Determination (R²) test, an R value of 0.788 was obtained, indicating a strong relationship between the independent variables collectively and the dependent variable. An R-squared (R²) value of 0.620 indicates that the service quality variables (Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy) collectively account for 62.0% of the variation in customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari.

t-Test (Partial)

The t-test aims to test the partial effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable, with the hypothesis acceptance criterion being if t-calculated > t-table or significance < 0.05. With df = 84 (n = 90; k = 5) and $\alpha = 0.05$ (two-tailed test), the t-table value is 1.989.

Table 6. Results of the t-Test (Partial)

Hypothesis	t-calculated	t-table	Sig.	Conclusion
H1: Tangibles (X ₁) on Customer Satisfaction (Y)	1.989	1.989	0.050	Accepted
H2: Reliability (X ₂) on Customer Satisfaction (Y)	2.201	1.989	0.030	Accepted
H3: Responsiveness (X ₃) on Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0.727	1.989	0.469	Rejected
H4: Assurance (X ₄) on Customer Satisfaction (Y)	1.803	1.989	0.075	Rejected
H5: Empathy (X ₅) on Customer Satisfaction (Y)	3.671	1.989	0.000	Accepted

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 6, the variables Reliability (X₂) and Empathy (X₅) were found to have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction, as evidenced by significance values of 0.030 and 0.000, respectively. Specifically, Empathy is the most dominant predictor with a regression coefficient of 0.409 and the highest t-value (3.671). The Tangibles variable (X₁) is also marginally accepted (sig. = 0.050; t-value = 1.989), meaning that physical evidence also contributes to satisfaction. Conversely, the Responsiveness (X₃) and Assurance (X₄) variables had no significant effect (sig. > 0.05), so H₃ and H₄ were rejected.

F-Test (Simultaneous)

The F-test was conducted to determine the combined (simultaneous) effect of all independent variables on the dependent variable. The null hypothesis is rejected if the calculated F-value is greater than the critical F-value or if the significance level is less than 0.05. The critical F-value with df1 = 5 and df2 = 84 at $\alpha = 0.05$ is 2.323.

Table 7. Results of the F-Test (Simultaneous)

Model	Calculated F	Table F	Sig	Conclusion
Regression	27.465	2.323	0.000	Accepted (H ₆)

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 7, the calculated F-value is 27.465 > the critical F-value of 2.323, with a significance level of 0.000 < 0.05. Thus, H₆ is accepted, meaning that the variables Tangibles (X₁), Reliability (X₂), Responsiveness (X₃), Assurance (X₄), and Empathy (X₅) collectively (simultaneously) have a significant effect on customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari.

4.2 Discussion

The Effect of Tangibles on Customer Satisfaction

The t-test results indicate that Tangibles (X₁) has a positive effect on customer satisfaction (t-calculated = 1.989; sig. = 0.050). It should be explicitly noted that this significance value is exactly at the $\alpha = 0.05$ threshold, so the effect is marginal. This indicates that although the physical conditions of BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari’s services such as facilities, equipment, and staff appearance have been perceived as adequate by customers and contribute to satisfaction, this dimension is not the primary driver compared to other dimensions. This finding aligns with the study by Amalia et al. (2020), which confirms that physical evidence has a positive effect, albeit with weaker strength in this context.

The Effect of Reliability on Customer Satisfaction

The Reliability variable (X_2) has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction (t-value = 2.201; sig. = 0.030). This indicates that the BUMDes' ability to provide accurate, consistent, and reliable services is a crucial factor for customer satisfaction. This finding supports the study by Mabtukha & Suryaningsih (2024), which confirms that service reliability significantly influences BUMDes customer satisfaction, where customers will be satisfied if the services received align with their expectations and are free from procedural errors.

The Effect of Responsiveness on Customer Satisfaction

The results of the hypothesis testing indicate that the responsiveness variable (X_3) does not have a significant effect on customer satisfaction in a partial analysis (t-value = 0.727; sig. = 0.469), so H_3 is rejected. This phenomenon can be understood through the lens of relationship marketing and the rural socio-cultural context. Interactions at BUMDes tend to be long-term and based on familiarity (high-context culture), making the quality of interpersonal relationships more crucial than mere administrative response speed (Ghosh et al., 2021; Hasan et al., 2023). Moreover, savings and loan services and payments in rural areas are generally not time-critical, so customers are more tolerant of queues as long as transactions are fair and transparent. Although not statistically significant, the low average responsiveness (14.43) underscores the importance of optimizing queues and service procedures to maintain quality perceptions in the future.

The Effect of Assurance on Customer Satisfaction

The Assurance variable (X_4) yielded a t-value of 1.803 with a significance level of 0.075 (> 0.05), so H_4 is rejected. This finding indicates that service assurance (staff competence, transaction security, and courtesy) does not independently drive an increase in customer satisfaction. These results align with the theory of a trust-based economy in rural microfinance institutions, where public trust in BUMDes is largely built through long-established institutional ties and social capital, rather than solely through perceptions of individual staff competence (Tagar, 2024). In other words, assurance in this context has become a hygiene factor a basic requirement whose presence is expected but does not provide significant added value to satisfaction once it is met.

The Influence of Empathy on Customer Satisfaction

The results of the hypothesis testing indicate that the empathy variable (X_5) has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction (t-value = 3.671; sig. = 0.000). With a regression coefficient of 0.409, empathy is the most dominant dimension influencing customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari. This reflects customers' high appreciation for personal attention, ease of communication, and staff understanding of their needs, which aligns with the characteristics of rural communities that prioritize interpersonal relationships. This finding supports the study by Hasan et al. (2023), which confirms that empathy-based customer orientation is a key factor in enhancing satisfaction at BUMDes. This finding also indicates that BUMDes customers evaluate service quality not only based on technical aspects of the service but also on the quality of interpersonal relationships formed during the service process. In the context of Balinese society, which is characterized by collectivism and a focus on social relationships, personal attention from staff is perceived as a form of appreciation and recognition of customers. Therefore, the dimension of empathy functions not only as a service attribute but also as a mechanism for building long-term customer trust and loyalty

The Simultaneous Influence of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction

Simultaneously, all dimensions of service quality (Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy) have a significant effect on customer satisfaction, with a calculated F-value of 27.465 $>$ the critical F-value of 2.323 and a p-value of 0.000 $<$ 0.05. The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.620 indicates that the model explains 62.0% of the variation in customer satisfaction.

These results support H6 and are consistent with the research by Afika & Harmawan (2025) and Mabtukha & Suryaningsih (2024), which states that service quality simultaneously has a significant effect on BUMDes customer satisfaction. These findings emphasize the importance of comprehensive and synergistic service quality management to improve customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari.

5. CONCLUSION

The results of this study provide practical implications for BUMDes managers in formulating strategies to improve service quality. The primary priority for is to strengthen staff interpersonal competencies through training in communication, customer-centric service, and complaint handling. Additionally, management must ensure service consistency by implementing clear standard operating procedures (SOPs) and a sustainable performance evaluation system. Thus, service quality improvement should not only focus on operational efficiency but also on building long-term relationships with customers.

It must be emphasized first that the results of this study are specific to the operational and socio-cultural context of BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari; therefore, they cannot be generalized to all BUMDes in Bali without further comparative analysis. Based on the analysis results, service quality which includes tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy simultaneously has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction at BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari. This is indicated by a calculated F-value of 27.465 with a significance level of 0.000 and a coefficient of determination of 62.0%, meaning that service quality explains the majority of the variation in customer satisfaction. Partially, the dimensions of tangibles, reliability, and empathy were found to have a significant influence, while responsiveness and assurance did not yet show a significant influence. Among all dimensions, empathy emerged as the most dominant factor in enhancing customer satisfaction, indicating that personal attention, effective communication, and understanding of customer needs are highly valued by the village community as users of BUMDes services.

Implicitly, these findings confirm that BUMDes development strategies in areas with strong socio-cultural ties cannot rely solely on procedural standardization or administrative speed; instead, they must prioritize interpersonal approaches, adaptive communication, and service adjustments based on local wisdom to maintain long-term customer satisfaction and loyalty. Theoretically, this study reinforces the relevance of the SERVQUAL model in explaining customer satisfaction within village economic institutions. However, the research results indicate that the strength of influence of each dimension is not always consistent and is significantly influenced by the socio-cultural context of the community. The finding that the empathy dimension is a dominant factor provides empirical support for the relationship marketing perspective, which emphasizes the importance of the quality of interpersonal relationships in building customer satisfaction.

This study has several limitations. First, the research object focused only on one BUMDes, so the generalizability of the results remains limited. Second, the study employed only a quantitative approach, thus failing to delve deeply into customer experiences when using BUMDes services. Third, the research model explains only 62.0% of the variation in customer satisfaction, indicating that other factors outside the model such as price, trust, organizational image, relationship quality, and digital literacy potentially influence customer satisfaction.

Based on the research findings, it is recommended that the management of BUMDes Pandak Bandung Mesari implement a series of operational strategies, including the conduct of continuous training programs for frontline staff to enhance communication skills, complaint handling, and the implementation of standard operating procedures (SOPs), as well as the optimization of human resources through the addition of operational staff or the implementation of a flexible shift system

during peak hours (09:00–12:00 and 14:00–16:00 WITA) to reduce queues and speed up service response times; furthermore, for future research, it is recommended to expand the scope of the study by adding moderator or mediator variables such as members' digital literacy, trust based on local wisdom, and community participation in decision-making, thereby enabling a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of BUMDes sustainability in the Bali region.

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